

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE
AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

DOCUMENTATION OF RISIS DATASETS VICO (version 6.0)

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1 Basic Characteristics

The VICO data infrastructure (version 6.0) contains geographical, industry and accounting information on companies founded starting from 1/1/1988, which have received at least one Venture Capital (VC) investment starting from 1/1/1998 up to 31/12/2021, operating in the 27 countries of the European Union, plus United Kingdom and Israel and information on their investment deals (e.g. deal date, total amount invested). VICO covers an overall number of 53,714 companies, that have been involved in 81,801 VC investment deals.

The aim of the VICO dataset is to create a unique data infrastructure with a substantial coverage of VC activity in Europe. The current version 6.0 of the VICO dataset extends the previous version 5.0 by adding VC investments up to 2021 and accounting data up to 2022 (previously available respectively up to 2018 and 2020);

Its uniqueness lies in the overall number of companies, the country coverage, and the extent of information gathered, thanks to the combination of multiple secondary data sources, namely Thompson Eikon, Bureau van Dijk Zephyr, Crunchbase and Bureau van Dijk Orbis.

Services currently offered by the VICO infrastructure allows to address a wide range of research questions concerning the characteristics, the evolution and the role of VC in Europe. It has been widely used by a large academic community to study the peculiarities of the European VC market and the effectiveness of different forms of VC in supporting the performance of European start-ups. Results from academic research based on VICO also attracted the attention of policy makers interested in assessing the impact of policy measures aimed at facilitating access to start-up finance.

The legal name of the operating organization is POLITECNICO DI MILANO, Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering, located in VIA LAMBRUSCHINI 4/B, MILANO, 20156, Italy represented by Raffaella Cagliano, Head of Department (or his authorized representative).

The VICO dataset access manager is Benedetta Montanaro (benedetta.montanaro@polimi.it).

2 Database content

2.1 Definition and description of observations

The database includes 53,714 companies founded starting from 1/1/1988, which have received at least one venture capital investment starting from 1/1/1998 up to 31/12/2021, operating in the 27 countries of the European Union, plus United Kingdom and Israel. VICO provides basic information on 17,690 distinct investors, of which 12,925 Venture Capitalists (VCs) and 4,233 Business Angels (BAs), plus a small percentage of other investors (e.g. crowdfunding, incubators/accelerators...). It also includes 750 equity CF investment deals located in the UK (i.e. the largest equity CF market in Europe) in the period 2011-2018. Companies and investors have been involved in 81,801 investment deals, for a total of 151,217 observations (as one or more investors can be involved in each single investment round).

The data infrastructure is organized in the following six tables:

1. **Companies**, which contains information on basic companies' characteristics. The unit of observation is the VC-backed company;
2. **Investments**, which contains information on VC deals (e.g. deal date, amount invested, investors involved, ...). The main unit of observation is the VC deal (i.e. the company-date-investor triad);
3. **Investors**, which contains information on basic investors' characteristics. The unit of observation is the investor;
4. **Accounting**, which contains accounting data of VC-backed companies. The main unit of observation is the company-year dyad;
5. **Exits**, which contains information on M&A and IPO deals conducted by VC-backed companies. The main unit of observation is the M&A/IPO deal (i.e. the company-date-acquirer triad).
6. **Equity CF Investments**, which contains information on equity CF deals. The main unit of observation is the equity CF campaign-date dyad.

2.2 Data acquisition and processing

In order to identify companies, investors and investment deals, we considered three main sources of information: Thompson Eikon, Bureau van Dijk Zephyr and Crunchbase.

The data collection process consisted in five main steps:

1. Definition of a unique list of companies and investors from the three source databases and organization of VC investment deals.
2. Data collection and organization of accounting information.
3. Data collection and organization of M&A/IPO activity.
4. Data collection and organization of equity CF investments.
5. Geocoding.
6. Collection of additional information on Corporate VCs and companies' business models.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

Table 1-6 describe variables names, descriptions and types.

Table 1 – Companies Table

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	VICO ID for companies
CompanyName	string	Company name
CompanyName_Orbis	string	Company name from Orbis
CompanyOtherNames	string	Other company names
CompanyNation	string	Company country
CompanyCity	string	Company city
CompanyAdress	string	Company address
CompanyZipCode	string	Company ZipCode
CompanyFoundedYear	float	Company year of foundation
NACERev2corecode4digits_Orbis	string	Company NACERev2 core code from Orbis

NACERev2corcodesdes_Orbis	string	Company NACERev2 core code description from Orbis
FirstInvestmentYear	float	Company year of first investment received
CompanyLong	float	Company longitude
CompanyLat	float	Company latitude
CompanyNUTS3Name	string	Name of the company NUTS3
CompanyNUTS3	string	Code of the company NUTS3
CompanyFUAName	string	Name of the company FUA
CompanyFUAAUniqueID	string	Cortex ID of the company FUA
CompanyFUACode	string	Code of the company FUA
CompanyRuralName	string	Name of the company Rural Area
CompanyRuralUniqueID	string	Cortex ID of the company Rural Area
CompanyRuralCode	string	Code of the company Rural Area
CompanyBusinessModel	string	Description of the business model

Table 2 - Investments Table

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	VICO ID for companies
InvestorID	string	VICO ID for investors
InvestmentDate	float	Date of investment round
InvestmentYear	float	Year of investment round
TotalEquityInvested_round_thEUR	string	Total equity investment in the investment round in thEUR

Table 3 - Investors Tables

Variable	Type	Description
InvestorID	string	VICO ID for investors
InvestorName	string	Investor name
InvestorOtherNames	string	Investor other names according to different data sources
InvestorNation	string	Investor country
InvestorCity	string	Investor city
InvestorLong	float	Investor longitude
InvestorLat	float	Investor latitude
InvestorNUTS3Name	string	Name of the investor NUTS3
InvestorNUTS3	string	Code of the investor NUTS3
InvestorFUAName	string	Name of the investor FUA
InvestorFUAAUniqueID	string	Cortex ID of the investor FUA
InvestorFUACode	string	Code of the investor FUA
InvestorRuralName	string	Name of the investor Rural Area
InvestorRuralUniqueID	string	Cortex ID of the investor Rural Area
InvestorRuralCode	string	Code of the investor Rural Area
InvestorType	string	Investor Type
CVC_autonomy	string	Level of autonomy of the CVC from the parent company
CVC_separateWebsite	boolean	Dummy = 1 if the CVC investor has a separate website

CVC_Mission	string	Mission of the CVC: whether the investor pursue strategic or financial objectives (or both), according to the CVC's mission statement
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Table 4 – Accounting Table

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	VICO ID for companies
Year	float	Year to which the accounting data refers to
FixedassetsthEUR	float	Total amount (after depreciation) of non current assets. (Intangible assets+Tangible assets+Other fixed assets). Thousand Euro. Nominal
ruIntangiblefixedassetsthEUR	float	All intangibles assets (after depreciation). Thousand Euro. Nominal
TangiblefixedassetsthEUR	float	All tangibles assets (after depreciation). Thousand Euro. Nominal
OtherfixedassetsthEUR	float	All other Fixed Assets (after depreciation). Thousand Euro. Nominal
CurrentassetsthEUR	float	Total amount of current assets. (Stocks+Debtors+Other current assets). Thousand Euro. Nominal
StockthEUR	float	Total inventories. Thousand Euro. Nominal
DebtorsthEUR	float	Trade receivables. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthercurrentassetsthEUR	float	All other current assets. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CashcashequivalentthEUR	float	Detail of other current assets=amount of cash at bank and in hand of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
TotalassetsthEUR	float	Total Assets. (Fixed assets+Current assets). Thousand Euro. Nominal
ShareholdersfundsthEUR	float	Total Equity (Capital+Other shareholders funds). Thousand Euro. Nominal
CapitalthEUR	float	Issued Share capital. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthershareholdersfundsthEUR	float	All shareholders funds not linked with the Issued capital. Thousand Euro. Nominal
NoncurrentliabilitiesthEUR	float	All long-term liabilities of the company. (Long term debts+Other non current liabilities+Provisions). Thousand Euro. Nominal
LongtermdebtthEUR	float	Long-term financial debts to credit institutions (>1Year). Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthernoncurrentliabthEUR	float	All long-term liabilities not related to financial institutions (including Provisions). Thousand Euro. Nominal
ProvisionsthEUR	float	Detail of other non current liabilities=Provisions. Thousand Euro. Nominal

CurrentliabilitiesthEUR	float	All current liabilities of the company (Loans+Creditors+Other current liabilities). Thousand Euro. Nominal
LoansthEUR	float	Short-term financial debts to credit institutions (<1Year). Thousand Euro. Nominal
CreditorsthEUR	float	All debts to suppliers and contractors. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthercurrentliabilitiesthEUR	float	All current liabilities not payable to financial institutions nor trade debts. Thousand Euro. Nominal
TotalsharefundsliabthEUR	float	Total Shareholders Equity and liabilities. (Shareholders funds+Non current liabilities+Current liabilities). Thousand Euro. Nominal to drop
WorkingcapitalthEUR	float	Net working capital (Stocks+Debtors-Creditors). Thousand Euro. Nominal
NetcurrentassetsthEUR	float	Net current assets (Current Assets-Current liabilities). Thousand Euro. Nominal
EnterprisevaluethEUR	float	Sum of the Market capitalisation, the Long term debts and the Loans (to financial institutions) minus the Cash and cash equivalent (for listed companies only). Thousand Euro. Nominal
TurnoverthEUR	float	Total operating revenues (Net sales+Other operating revenues+Stocks variations). Thousand Euro. Nominal
SalesthEUR	float	Net sales. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CostsofgoodssoldthEUR	float	Costs of sold goods, production and services. Thousand Euro. Nominal
GrossprofitthEUR	float	Turnover – Costs of goods sold. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OtheroperatingexpensesthEUR	float	All costs not directly related to the production of goods sold. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OperatingPLEBITthEUR	float	Earnings before interests and taxes (Gross profit – Other operating expenses). Thousand Euro. Nominal
FinancialrevenuethEUR	float	All financial revenues (interests, incomes from shares,..). Thousand Euro. Nominal
FinancialexpensesthEUR	float	All financial expenses (interest charges, write-off financial assets,..). Thousand Euro. Nominal
FinancialPLthEUR	float	Resut from financial activities. (Financial revenues – Financial expenses). Thousand Euro. Nominal
PLbeforetaxthEUR	float	Earnings before taxes. (Operating profit+Financial profit). Thousand Euro. Nominal
TaxationthEUR	float	All taxes paid by the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
PLaftertaxthEUR	float	Earnings after taxes. (Profit before taxation – Taxation) Thousand Euro. Nominal

ExtrandotherrevenuethEUR	float	All extraordinary revenues and other revenues not belonging to the ordinary activities of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExtrandotherexpensesthEUR	float	All extraordinary expenses and other rexpenses not belonging to the ordinary activities of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExtrandotherPLthEUR	float	All extraordinary and other result not belonging to the ordinary activities of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
PLforperiodNetincomethEUR	float	Net income for the Year. (Profit after taxation+Extraordinary and other profit). Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExportrevenuethEUR	float	Revenues from exports. Thousand Euro. Nominal
MaterialcoststhEUR	float	Detail of the cost of materials used only for goods produced. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CostsofemployeesthEUR	float	Detail of all the employees costs of the company (including pension costs). Thousand Euro. Nominal
DepreciationAmortthEUR	float	Total amount of depreciations and amortizations of the assets. Thousand Euro. Nominal
InterestpaidthEUR	float	Total amount of interest charges paid for shares or loans. Thousand Euro. Nominal
RDexpensesthEUR	float	Total amount of R&D expenses. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CashflowthEUR	float	Profit for period+Depreciation. Thousand Euro. Nominal
AddedvaluethEUR	float	Profit for period+Depreciation+Taxation+Interests paid+Cost of employees. Thousand Euro. Nominal
EBITDAthEUR	float	Operating profit+Depreciation. Thousand Euro. Nominal
Numberofemployees	float	Total number of full time employees of the company

Table 5 – Exits Table

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	VICO ID for companies
AcqDealNumber	string	Zephyr ID for acquisition deals
Acquirorname	string	Name of the acquirer
Acquirorcountrycode	string	Country code of the acquirer
AcqDealtype	string	Description of the Acquisition Deal with sold ownership
AcqDealvaluethEUR	float	Acquisition Deal value in th EUR
AcquirorBvDIDnumber	string	CompanyBvDID of the acquiror

AcqDate	float	Date in which the Acquisition was completed, otherwise completed assumed, otherwise announced
AcqYear	float	Year in which the Acquisition was completed, otherwise completed assumed, otherwise announced
Acquisition_dummy	boolean	Dummy equal to 1 if the company was acquired (ownership sold > 50%), 0 otherwise
IPODealNumber	string	Zephyr ID for IPO deals
IPODealvaluethEUR	float	IPO Deal value in th EUR
IPODate	float	Date in which the IPO was completed, otherwise completed assumed, otherwise announced
IPOYear	float	Year in which the IPO was completed, otherwise completed assumed, otherwise announced
IPOStockExchange	string	Stock Exchange of the IPO
IPO_dummy	boolean	Dummy equal to 1 if the company went through an IPO

Table 6 –Equity CF Investments Table

Variable	Type	Description
IDEquityCF	string	VICO ID for Equity CF Campaign
CampaignName	string	Name of the Equity CF Campaign
EquityOfferedFirstCampaign	float	Amount of Equity Offered in the First Campaign
PostMoneyFirstCampaign	float	Post money valuation after First Campaign
CampaignDate	string	Date of the Campaign
CampaignYear	float	Year of the Campaign
CampaignAmountRaised	float	Raised amount in the Campaign
CampaignCategory	string	Description of Campaign Category
Platform	string	Name of the platform of the Equity CF Campaign
CompanyID	string	VICO ID for companies

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

Sectorial classification follows the NACE Rev. 2 classification. The distribution of companies according to the NACE Rev. 2 Main Section is reported in Table 7.

Table 7: Sectorial coverage

NACE Rev. 2 Main Section	N. Companies	Percent
A – Agriculture, forestry and fishing	90	0.24
B – Mining and quarrying	78	0.21
C - Manufacturing	4,829	12.74
D - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	242	0.64
E - Water supply; sewerage, waste management	121	0.32

F - Construction	448	1.18
G - Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	3,341	8.81
H - Transportation and storage	363	0.96
I - Accommodation and food service activities	443	1.17
J - Information and communication	14,504	38.26
K - Financial and insurance activities	2,208	5.82
L - Real estate activities	417	1.10
M - Professional, scientific and technical activities	6,842	18.05
N - Administrative and support services activities	2,193	5.78
O - Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	9	0.02
P - Education	308	0.81
Q - Human health and social work activities	562	1.48
R - Arts, entertainment and recreation	328	0.87
S - Other service activities	578	1.52
T - Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods and services-producing activities of households for own use	6	0.02
U - Activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies	1	0.00
Total	37,911	100.00

The population of companies has been restricted to those founded starting from 1/1/1988, which received the first investment starting from 1/1/1998 up to 31/12/2021. Overall, start-ups are relatively young, with a median foundation year of 2011. Table 8 and 9 report the distribution of VC-backed companies by foundation year and year of the first investment received.

Table 8: Distribution of companies by foundation year

Foundation year	N. Companies	Percent
before 1990	518	1.28
1990≤y<1995	1,665	4.13
1995≤y<2000	4,010	9.94
2000≤y<2005	5,696	14.12
2005≤y<2010	6,569	16.28
2010≤y<2015	10,223	25.34
2015≤y≤2020	11,255	27.90
after 2020	402	1.00
Total	40,338	100.00

Table 9: Distribution of companies by year of first investment

First Investment Year	N. Companies	Percent
before 2000	1,573	2.93
2000≤y<2005	7,522	14.00
2005≤y<2010	6,391	11.90
2010≤y<2015	11,040	20.55
2015≤y≤2020	22,815	42.47

after 2020	4,373	8.14
Total	53,714	100.00

As to the temporal coverage of accounting data and M&A/IPO information, they are available respectively from 2005 to 2022 and from 1998 to 2023. Equity CF investments are available from 2011 to 2018.

As to the geographical coverage, the database includes information on the country, NUTS regions (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/regions-and-cities/overview>), Functional Urban and Rural Areas (<https://www.oecd.org/cfe/regional-policy/functionalurbanareasbycountry.htm>) and exact geographical coordinates (i.e. latitude and longitude). The geographical distribution according to the country in which the companies are located is reported in Table 10.

Table 10: Distribution of companies by country

Country	N. Companies	Percent
Austria	730	1.36
Belgium	1,204	2.25
Bulgaria	330	0.62
Croatia	161	0.30
Cyprus	108	0.20
Czech Republic	386	0.72
Denmark	1,219	2.27
Estonia	389	0.73
Finland	1,645	3.07
France	8,671	16.17
Germany	6,630	12.36
Greece	173	0.32
Hungary	743	1.39
Ireland	1,493	2.78
Israel	2,908	5.42
Italy	1,886	3.52
Latvia	246	0.46
Lithuania	219	0.41
Luxembourg	209	0.39
Malta	40	0.07
Netherlands	2,186	4.08
Poland	1,172	2.19
Portugal	724	1.35
Romania	258	0.48
Slovakia	119	0.22
Slovenia	92	0.17
Spain	3,233	6.03
Sweden	2,704	5.04
United Kingdom	13,752	25.64
Total	53,630	100.000

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

Table from 11 to 16 report the number of missing values and the percentage of missing values with respect to the total number of observations (i.e. the number of companies, investors and investment deals).

Table 11 – Missing information: Companies Table

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
CompanyID	0	53,714	0%
BvDIDnumber	11,581	53,714	21.56%
CompanyName	0	53,714	0%
CompanyName_Orbis	11,581	53,714	21.56%
CompanyOtherNames	27,399	53,714	51.01%
CompanyNation	84	53,714	0.16%
CompanyCity	815	53,714	1.52%
CompanyAddress	3,911	53,714	7.28%
CompanyZipCode	11,094	53,714	20.65%
CompanyFoundedYear	13,376	53,714	24.9%
NACERev2corecode4digits_Orbis	15,803	53,714	29.42%
NACERev2corcodesdes_Orbis	15,803	53,714	29.42%
FirstInvestmentYear	0	53,714	0%
CompanyLong	2,112	53,714	3.93%
CompanyLat	2,112	53,714	3.93%
CompanyNUTS3Name	6,876	53,714	12.8%
CompanyNUTS3	6,876	53,714	12.8%
CompanyFUAName	2,395	53,714	4.46%
CompanyFUAAUniqueID	2,395	53,714	4.46%
CompanyFUACode	2,395	53,714	4.46%
CompanyRuralName	2,395	53,714	4.46%
CompanyRuralUniqueID	2,395	53,714	4.46%
CompanyRuralCode	2,395	53,714	4.46%

Table 12 – Missing information: Investments Table

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
CompanyID	0	151,217	0%
InvestorID	0	151,217	0%
InvestmentDate	0	151,217	0%
InvestmentYear	0	151,217	0%
TotalEquityInvested_round_thEUR	44,391	151,217	29.36%

Table 13 – Missing information: Investors Table

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
InvestorID	0	17,690	0%
InvestorName	0	17,690	0%
InvestorOtherNames	5,851	17,690	33.08%
InvestorNation	1,895	17,690	10.71%

InvestorCity	3,895	17,690	22.02%
InvestorLong	8,432	17,690	47.67%
InvestorLat	8,432	17,690	47.67%
InvestorNUTS3Name	9,881	17,690	55.86%
InvestorNUTS3	9,881	17,690	55.86%
InvestorFUAName	8,613	17,690	48.69%
InvestorFUANUniqueID	8,622	17,690	48.74%
InvestorFUACode	8,613	17,690	48.69%
InvestorRuralName	8,613	17,690	48.69%
InvestorRuralUniqueID	8,622	17,690	48.74%
InvestorRuralCode	8,613	17,690	48.69%
InvestorType	0	17,690	0%
CVC_autonomy	1,598	17,690	9.03%
CVC_separateWebsite	1,598	17,690	9.03%
CVC_Mission	1,598	17,690	9.03%

Table 14 – Missing information: Accounting Table

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
CompanyID	0	499,861	0%
Year	0	499,861	0%
FixedassetsthEUR	349,184	499,861	69.86%
IntangiblefixedassetsthEUR	309,948	499,861	62.01%
TangiblefixedassetsthEUR	289,816	499,861	57.98%
OtherfixedassetsthEUR	361,806	499,861	72.38%
CurrentassetsthEUR	270,750	499,861	54.17%
StockthEUR	276,674	499,861	55.35%
DebtorsthEUR	275,635	499,861	55.14%
OthercurrentassetsthEUR	274,554	499,861	54.93%
CashcashequivalentthEUR	290,905	499,861	58.2%
TotalassetsthEUR	270,238	499,861	54.06%
ShareholdersfundsthEUR	269,765	499,861	53.97%
CapitalthEUR	272,465	499,861	54.51%
OthershareholdersfundsthEUR	273,419	499,861	54.7%
NoncurrentliabilitiesthEUR	272,613	499,861	54.54%
LongtermdebtthEUR	331,619	499,861	66.34%
OthernoncurrentliabthEUR	331,678	499,861	66.35%
ProvisionsthEUR	360,297	499,861	72.08%
CurrentliabilitiesthEUR	270,678	499,861	54.15%
LoansthEUR	297,579	499,861	59.53%
CreditorsthEUR	296,704	499,861	59.36%
OthercurrentliabilitiesthEUR	292,630	499,861	58.54%
TotalsharefundsliabthEUR	270,123	499,861	54.04%
WorkingcapitalthEUR	319,918	499,861	64.00%
NetcurrentassetsthEUR	312,725	499,861	62.56%
EnterprisevaluethEUR	493,029	499,861	98.63%
TurnoverthEUR	359,183	499,861	71.86%
SalesthEUR	386,956	499,861	77.41%
CostsofgoodssoldthEUR	456,138	499,861	91.25%

GrossprofitthEUR	442,549	499,861	88.53%
OtheroperatingexpensesthEUR	419,726	499,861	83.97%
OperatingPLEBITthEUR	348,875	499,861	69.79%
FinancialrevenuethEUR	379,995	499,861	76.02%
FinancialexpensesthEUR	367,396	499,861	73.5%
FinancialPLthEUR	348,591	499,861	69.74%
PLbeforetaxthEUR	348,820	499,861	69.78%
TaxationthEUR	380,724	499,861	76.17%
PLaftertaxthEUR	355,953	499,861	71.21%
ExtrandotherrevenuethEUR	448,087	499,861	89.64%
ExtrandotherexpensesthEUR	463,352	499,861	92.7%
ExtrandotherPLthEUR	451,015	499,861	90.23%
PLforperiodNetincomethEUR	349,933	499,861	70.01%
ExportrevenuethEUR	461,625	499,861	92.35%
MaterialcoststhEUR	430,382	499,861	86.1%
CostsofemployeesthEUR	372,584	499,861	74.54%
DepreciationAmortthEUR	344,628	499,861	68.94%
InterestpaidthEUR	392,090	499,861	78.44%
RDexpensesthEUR	489,243	499,861	97.88%
CashflowthEUR	377,530	499,861	75.53%
AddedvaluethEUR	416,801	499,861	83.38%
EBITDAthEUR	369,792	499,861	73.98%
Numberofemployees	334,389	499,861	66.9%

Table 15 – Missing information: Exits Table

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
CompanyID	0	5,345	0%
AcqDealNumber	0	5,345	0%
Acquirorname	19	5,345	0.36%
Acquirorcountrycode	58	5,345	1.85%
AcqDealtype	0	5,345	0%
AcqDealvaluethEUR	2,938	5,345	54.97%
AcquirorBvDIDnumber	203	5,345	3.78%
AcqDate	0	5,345	0%
AcqYear	0	5,345	0%
Acquisition_dummy	0	5,345	0%
IPODealNumber	0	5,345	0%
IPODealvaluethEUR	100	5,345	1.87%
IPODate	0	5,345	0%
IPOYear	0	5,345	0%
IPOStockExchange	124	5,345	2.32%
IPO_dummy	0	5,345	0%

Table 16 – Missing information: Equity CF Investments

Variable	N. missing	Total Obs.	% missing
IDEquityCF	0	750	0%
CampaignName	0	750	0%

EquityOfferedFirstCampaign	44	750	17.6%
PostMoneyFirstCampaign	44	750	17.6%
CampaignDate	0	750	0%
CampaignYear	0	750	0%
CampaignAmountRaised	3	750	0.4%
CampaignCategory	242	750	32.27%
Platform	0	750	0%
CompanyID	0	750	0%

3 Technical Specifications

3.1 Information on the data base system

The database is currently available in .csv and STATA (.dta) format.

3.2 Description of the Entity Relationship Model (if applicable)

Not applicable.

3.3 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures (if applicable)

The VICO dataset is integrated into the RISIS Core Facility (RCF) with other firm-level RISIS databases. In particular, integration is made possible through the use of FirmReg, a register that uniquely identifies and tracks over time companies included in different RISIS datasets, such as CIB on the largest innovative industrial firms worldwide, Cheetah on European mid-size fast growing firms and VICO. Each VICO company is connected to FirmReg through unambiguous and stable (over time) identifiers.

At the geographical level, VICO is harmonized with the other research infrastructures in RISIS by adopting the RISIS Cortext geocoding service, NUTS classification of administrative units (as provided by Eurostat) and the Functional Urban and Rural Areas classification (as provided by the OECD).

Integration of VICO in the RCF will be allowed with anonymised company names, which is essential for legal issues due to data retrieval from different commercial databases. Only in specific cases when a high level of data protection is guaranteed, such as in case of physical visits and direct research collaborations with the datasets' owners, companies' names may be disclosed.

4 Scientific use cases and main references

Given the fine-grained and wide scope of data on VC-backed firms, VICO can be used to produce large scale evidence on the ecology of the VC landscape in Europe, extending current empirical evidence based on the previous version of the dataset. In particular, promising avenues of research include:

- VC investment patterns and selection process, e.g. how different types of VCs select their portfolio firms (see Bertoni et al., 2015a; Colombo and Shafi, 2016; Bertoni et al., 2019), e.g.

European v. US VCs' peculiar investment criteria, how different types of VCs select their portfolio firms;

- The treatment effect of VCs on invested companies, e.g. the effect of VC value added activities on portfolio firms' performance in terms of growth and valuation performance (Croce et al., 2013; Grilli and Murtinu, 2014; Colombo and Murtinu, 2017; Cumming et al., 2017; Colombo & Montanaro, 2023)
- The internationalization and geography of VC activity in Europe, e.g. the emergence and/or agglomeration of VC markets around big metropolitan areas, the attraction of cross-border investments (Devigne et al., 2013; Bertoni and Groh, 2014; Colombo et al., 2021; Guerini and Hong, 2020; Guerini and Tenca, 2018; D'Adda et. al 2020);
- The complementarities between VCs and other sources of finance (i.e. BAs, crowdfunding...) thanks to VICO coverage of different types of investors in addition to VCs (Butticè et al., 2020; Capizzi et al., 2022);
- The link between innovation (e.g. radical inventions) and financing decisions of VCs (Colombo et al., 2023);
- The investigation of the pricing obtained by VC-backed and non-VC-backed entrepreneurial ventures in ECF campaigns (Montanaro et al., 2023);
- The effect of VC on startups' internationalization strategy, measured through startups' trademark activity filed at EU level (Guerini et al., 2023);
- The investigation of the relation between stereotypical trust and the formation of initial ties between new ventures and corporate venture capitalists (CVC) (Colombo et al., 2023);
- The certification effect and removal of financial constraints of portfolio firms (e.g. Guerini and Quas, 2016; Bertoni et al., 2015b);

Moreover, the broad longitudinal timeframe (1998-2021) gives the opportunity to study the effects of the financial crisis on VC activity, while the coverage of different types of investors, in addition to VCs (e.g., BAs) allows to investigate the complementarities between VCs and other sources of finance.

In what follows, we provide an overview of a selection of published and working papers based on VICO.

Colombo et al. (2021), as part of the policy brief series developed within RISIS2, aims at providing novel evidence about the geographical distribution of VC activity in Europe and Israel over the 2010-2018 period. The findings have important policy implications for democratizing the access to VC in more peripheral areas and for the development of entrepreneurial ecosystems. More precisely, using data of VICO 5.0, the research describes the agglomeration patterns of VC activity at the regional, metropolitan and industry-level. The main findings include: i) VC deals are unevenly distributed across countries, the UK and France are the most relevant VC markets in terms of number of VC deals, while Eastern European countries and Israel show the highest incidence rates (VC deals / GDP) (see Figure 2); ii) VC activity is mostly concentrated in large metropolitan areas, but there is a non-negligible share of VC activity in more peripheral areas; iii) there has been an increasing concentration of VC activity in large metropolitan areas from 2010 to 2018 (see Figure 4); and iv) important differences emerge across sectors. The life science sector exhibits higher dispersion of VC deals outside the main VC hubs, mainly in areas with relevant knowledge creation activity. Conversely, VC activity in

the Software, Internet & TLC and R&D & engineering sectors is concentrating in large metropolitan areas.

Butticè et al. (2020), using a unique dataset of 290 firms that successfully fundraised via the two most prominent UK equity crowdfunding portals and combining it with VICO, examine how different shareholder structures, i.e. the nominee vs. the direct shareholder structure, affect the attraction of subsequent VC financing. Results shows that: i) receiving equity crowdfunding facilitates the attraction of VC financing, ii) this association is stronger when the firm selected a nominee shareholder structure, iii) compared to BA-backed firms, equity crowdfunding through a nominee structure eases VC attraction.

Guerini and Hong (2020) examine whether there are positive externalities associated with international VC firms' penetration in the European VC market. The study focuses on how the presence of foreign VC firms in the local market affects performances of start-ups backed by domestic investors. Results suggest that domestic VC firms can obtain valuable know-how through forming syndicates with foreign VC firms, as prior experience with foreign VC firms is associated to greater performance of domestic VC investments.

Montanaro et al. (2023) investigate i) the pricing obtained by VC-backed and non-VC-backed UK entrepreneurial ventures in 695 successful and unsuccessful ECF campaigns launched between 2011 and 2018 on Crowdcube; and ii) if being VC-backed before the launch of the ECF campaign reduces the likelihood to fail after the campaign (Montanaro et al., 2022). This work testifies the usage of VICO 5.0 infrastructure to study the relationship between different financing channels for startups, i.e., VC and crowdfunding. Results show that, in ECF, VC-backed firms obtain higher pricing than non-VC-backed firms, but, contrarily to expectations, they are not less likely to fail after the campaign, or to be more likely to survive with higher credit rating. In other words, being VC-backed is costly and easily observable by the crowd, which thus concede higher pricing to VC-backed companies in ECF, coherently with the results of previous studies on the campaign success likelihood. However, a long-run separating equilibrium fails to be generated.

Guerini et al. (2023) combined VICO 5.0 with the ISI-Trademark Data Collection dataset on trademarks, also developed within the RISIS2 project, and focus on the effect of Venture Capital on startups' internationalization strategy, measured through startups' trademark activity filed at EU level (Guerini et al., 2023). To assess whether the receipt of VC effectively influences the subsequent international trademark activity of a selected startup, the authors first built a control group of firms that mirrors their sample of VC-backed, then related different trademark-based indicators, namely trademark stock and trademark portfolio extension, i.e., trademark breadth, to different VC characteristics. Results suggest that VC has a strong effect in boosting international investees' trademark activity, in terms of growth of the trademark stock. Moreover, the impact on trademark stock is stronger for larger VC syndicates, syndicates composed by VCs with more international experience and startups invested by foreign VCs.

5 References

- Bertoni, F., Colombo, M. G., & Quas, A. (2015a). The patterns of venture capital investment in Europe. *Small Business Economics*, 45(3), 543-560.
- Bertoni, F., Croce, A., & Guerini, M. (2015b). Venture capital and the investment curve of young high-tech companies. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 35, 159-176.
- Bertoni, F., & Groh, A. P. (2014). Cross-border investments and venture capital exits in Europe. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 22(2), 84-99.
- Butticè, V., Di Pietro, F., & Tenca, F. (2020). Is equity crowdfunding always good? Deal structure and the attraction of venture capital investors. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 65, 101773.
- Capizzi, V., Croce, A., & Tenca, F. (2022). Do Business Angels' Investments Make It Easier to Raise Follow-on Venture Capital Financing? An Analysis of the Relevance of Business Angels' Investment Practices. *British Journal of Management*, 33(1), 306-326.
- Colombo, M. G., & Shafi, K. (2016). Swimming with Sharks in Europe: When are They Dangerous and What Can New Ventures Do to Defend Themselves? *Strategic Management Journal*, 37(11), 2307-2322.
- Colombo, M. G., & Murtinu, M. (2017). Venture Capital Investments in Europe and Portfolio Firms' Economic Performance: Independent versus Corporate Investors. *Journal of Economics & Management Strategy*, 26(1), 35-66.
- Colombo, M. G., Guerini, M., & Tenca, F. (2021). Policy Brief, Issue 7/Democratising access to smart money in EU: evidence from the VICO dataset. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4697328>.
- Colombo, M.G., Guerini, M., Hoisl, K. & Zeiner, N. (2023). The Dark Side of Signals: Patents Protecting Radical Inventions and Venture Capital Investments. *Research Policy*, 52(5), 104741. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2023.104741>
- Colombo, M.G. & Montanaro, B. (2023). Signal sequences: Venture Capital, IPO and Startup Valuation at Acquisitions. Working paper. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3919140>.
- Croce, A., Martí, J., & Murtinu, S. (2013). The impact of venture capital on the productivity growth of European entrepreneurial firms: 'Screening' or 'value added' effect? *Journal of Business Venturing*, 28(4), 489-510.
- Cumming, D. J., Grilli, L., & Murtinu, S. (2017). Governmental and independent venture capital investments in Europe: A firm-level performance analysis. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 42, 439- 459.
- D'Adda, D., Guerini, M. & Quas, A. (2020). Distant friends and close enemies: Sub-national cultural distance and Venture Capital investments. Working paper. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3906330>.
- Devigne, D., Vanacker, T., Manigart, S., & Paeleman, I. (2013). The role of domestic and cross- border venture capital investors in the growth of portfolio companies. *Small Business Economics*, 40(3), 553-573.
- Grilli, L., & Murtinu, S. (2014). Government, venture capital and the growth of European high-tech entrepreneurial firms. *Research Policy*, 43(9), 1523-1543.
- Guerini, M., & Quas, A. (2016). Governmental venture capital in Europe: Screening and certification. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 31(2), 175-195.
- Guerini, M. & Tenca, F. (2018). The geography of technology-intensive start-ups and venture capital: European evidence. *Journal of Industrial and Business Economics*, 45(3), 361-386. Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s40812-018-0098-9>.

Guerini, M. & Hong, S. (2020). Going Global to Stay Local: The Effect of International Syndication Experience on the Performance of Domestic Venture Capital Investments. Working paper. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3908422>.

Guerini, M., Tenca, F., & Neuhäusler, P. (2023). Effect of Venture Capital financing on startups' trademarks. Working Paper.

Montanaro, B., Manigart, S., & Vanacker, T. (2023). Venture Capital- Backing, the Pricing of Shares, and Post- Campaign Performance in Equity Crowdfunding. Working Paper.